

HIGHLY SENSITIVE GRAPHENE COMPOSITE STRAIN SENSOR FROM QUASI-STATIC TO ULTRASONIC WAVE

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Keywords: Graphene composite, Strain sensor, Broad band frequency, Acousto-ultrasonics, Structural health monitoring

1 INTRODUCTION

Strain sensors have been applied in various areas including bridges, ships, aerospace and so on^[1]. Traditional strain sensors are metal strain gauges and PZT. Metal strain gauges are usually utilized in static strain measurements and limited by their low gauge factor (~2). PZT has a much higher gauge factor in a range of 50 to 100 and it can response to dynamic strain up to 1.5 MHz. However, their shortcomings such as heavy weight, high cost, and excessive hardness for the incorporation into a complex structure, impose restrictions on the further application^[2]. While, nanocomposites made from nanofillers and polymer matrix can realize sensitive response to strain of different magnitudes from quasi-static strain to medium frequency vibration, and even up to high frequency ultrasonic wave, which exhibiting vast potential in human motion and structure health monitoring. The flexibility, surface compatibility, lightweight, low cost and simple fabrication method make it a promising candidate of traditional strain gauges^[3].

2 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

2.1 Fabrication of graphene-PVDF composite

The PVDF powder was solved in 1-Methyl-2-pyrrolidinone (NMP) (20 wt.%) at 70 °C for 3h. Then graphene aqueous solution (2.7 wt.%) was added to PVDF solution and the mixture was stirred by low speed mixer for 2h at speed of 800rpm. Afterwards, the mixer was poured on glass broad and cured at 150°C for 2h. After being cooled in air, the composite film can be achieved by peeling off from the glass broad.

2.2 Static strain response behavior

The fractional resistance change almost depends linearly on tension strain. The largest gauge factor is about 50 achieved by samples with a graphene content of 0.5 wt.% which is the percolation threshold calculated according to percolation theory. Nanocomposites exhibit sensitive, fast and stable response to small strains and 1% strain with different strain rate (0.5 ~10 %/min) as shown in Fig1.

Figure 1: (a) Resistance change for nanocomposites as a function of tension strain. (b) Resistance change under different small strain. (c) Stable resistance change under 1% strain for more than 2000 cycles. (d) Sensitive response to 1% strain with different strain rate.

2.3 Dynamic strain response behavior

Nanocomposites show sensitive response to dynamic strain from 0.1 Hz to several hundred kilohertz. In medium frequency cantilever vibration with frequency range of 100-10000 Hz, the amplitude displays a linear change with the excitation signal, revealing the elastic deformation of the composite to the micro disturbance. Furthermore, the nanocomposite also shows strong response to ultrasonic wave signal with frequency of 200 kHz, which is comparable with that of commercial PZT, indicating vast potential application prospects in structural health monitoring.

Figure 2: (a) Sensitive response of 1% low frequency strain. Sensitive response to medium frequency strain caused by cantilever vibration with (b) different frequency and (c) different voltage at 200Hz. (d) Sensitive response to high frequency of acousto-ultrasonic at 200kHz.

3 CONCLUSIONS

Inspired by an innovative sensing mechanism, a flexible carbon nanocomposites-based hybrid sensor, made of graphene and polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF), has been developed for acousto-ultrasonics-based structural health monitoring. The sensing performance of the developed sensor has been validated by in-situ acquiring strain signals from low frequency cyclic tensile loading, through medium frequency impact-induced acoustic emission signals, to high frequency ultrasonic guided

waves. It has been revealed that, owing to the recommendable mechanical and electrical properties of graphene added, the sensor can reach a high gauge factor up to 50 and be responsive to ultrasonic guided waves. Signals captured via the developed sensors show good consistency with the counterpart signals obtained by conventional piezoelectric sensors and strain gauges. With light weight and good chemical stability, the developed sensor can be coated, sprayed or embedded into engineering structures with favorable environmental adaptation whereas minimum weight penalty, to form a sensing coating for acousto-ultrasonics-based structural health monitoring.

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